

IMPORTANCE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP SKILLS AMONG STUDENT WITH LEARNING DISABILITIES

^aParthiban Govindasamy

^bNoraini Binti Abdullah

^cRohaizat Binti Ibrahim

^{abc}*University of Education Sultan Idris, Tanjong Malim, Malaysia*

^a*rthiban89@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT

Entrepreneurship is a best mechanism to boost up economy of a country. In addition, entrepreneurship skills fostering the innovation and productivity to develop the economy of a country as well as molding a person to be job creator rather than be a job seeker. Thus, entrepreneurship skills are an important key element towards enhancing an independent and productive living for student with learning disabilities. Student with learning disabilities is often categorized as unproductive children and neglected by the society. Students with learning disabilities are under-represented in the workforce, often facing discrimination by employers, and not served in good manner due to their inabilities. Hence, entrepreneurship skills are most powerful weapon to driven entrepreneurial spirit and giving practical competencies that enable to start an own business. In order to develop the entrepreneurship skills, government introduced entrepreneurship education in Malaysian National Curriculum in primary education, secondary education and tertiary education. However, entrepreneurship skills among students with learning disabilities remains behind in terms of research and the importance. Thus, more researches are very crucial on this field. Hence, the purpose of this study is to highlight the importance of entrepreneurship skills among students with learning disabilities. The impact of this study will provide a fundamental knowledge on the importance of entrepreneurship skills among student with learning disabilities for researchers in the future researches.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurship Skills, Learning Disabilities

1. Introduction

The research conducted by World Health Organization (2019) revealed there are currently more than 2 billion people confirmed as people with disabilities, that is 37.5% of the world's population. In Malaysia, based on Special Education Data ended 31 January 2020, it was found that a total of 88,352 students were categorized as students with special needs in Malaysia. According to the data, the number of students who are categorized as learning disabilities is very worrying. This is because a total of 72,683 students were categorized as students with learning disabilities out of 88,352 students with special needs, which is 82 % of the total number

of students with learning disabilities. Students with learning disabilities referred to those who are having retardation, disorder or delayed development in any one or more of the processes of speech, language, reading, spelling, writing, or arithmetic. These includes students with ADHD, autism, down syndrome, intellectual disability, retardation and dyslexia. Currently, this situation in Malaysia reflects global reality, where more and more people suffering from disabilities and the number of people with disabilities may increase over the time.

In many developed countries entrepreneurship skills considered as an opportunity or alternative pathway for person with disabilities to involve in job market (Widoyoko et al., (2018). This is because entrepreneurship skills able to break down the problems faced by the students with learning disabilities especially in finding for permanent job. Developing countries promoting entrepreneurship education or skills through education system to prepare them with entrepreneurship skills for contribute nation's economy. However, Noor Aini Ahmad (2015) found the students with learning disabilities such as down syndrome, autism, hyperactivity, mental retardation and learning disabilities such as dyslexia need support and guidance from individuals who are more knowledgeable in many things in their lives. So that, special education teachers should play an important role in guiding students with special needs to acquire entrepreneurship skills. Therefore, special education teachers need to cultivate the entrepreneurship skills among the students with learning disabilities through educational activities and trainings according to their level of ability.

Furthermore, those who are obtain entrepreneurship skills, they can apply those skills in employment or be able to create their own jobs. Entrepreneurship skills will step up their abilities to be a "job creator" than a "job seeker". In addition, the applied entrepreneurship skills are able to build alternative ideas and creativity to create jobs in the face problem of getting a job and not rely on salaried jobs alone (Anizam et al., 2020). This in turn can overcome the issues of unemployment and employment among students with learning disabilities.

On the other hand, a total of 35,061 students with special learning needs, which is 55 % of the 63,876 students studying in the Special Education Integration Program in Malaysian Primary Schools (Special Education Division, Ministry of Education Malaysia, 2020). Official Special Education Data clearly proves that a large number of students with learning disabilities are in the Integration Special Education Program in Primary Schools. So that, entrepreneurship skills should be tailored among students with learning disabilities since primary school across the curriculum.

Therefore, this paper aims to provide the importance of entrepreneurship skills among students with learning disabilities from various researchers and contexts. This paper will provide a fundamental knowledge on the importance of entrepreneurship skills among student with learning disabilities.

2. Literature Review

2.1 What Is Entrepreneurship and Entrepreneurs?

There are many definitions for entrepreneurship. Studies shows there is no standardized definition for entrepreneurship. Most of the definition based on the researchers' thoughts and their understanding. Entrepreneurs have certain identifiable attribute. Commonly,

entrepreneurship defined as a skill to start a new business. Besides, entrepreneur is an individual who creates a new business, bearing most of the risks and enjoying most of the rewards. In other words, the process of setting up a business is known as entrepreneurship.

Additionally, Schumpeter (1911) highlighted entrepreneur as an individual who introduces new products and services, or creates new forms of organisation, or exploits new raw material. Meanwhile, Low and McMillan (1998) define entrepreneurship is a creation of new enterprises. Thus, enterprise and entrepreneurship are interrelated in the effort of developing employability for the graduates (O'Leary, 2015). Though, Shane and Venkataraman (2007) says entrepreneurship does not have to include the creation of new organizations, it can also occur in existing organizations.

Bruyat and Julien (2000), explains entrepreneurship is a process where brought changes, that lead to generating new values and entrepreneur as a business founder. On the other hand, the entrepreneur is commonly seen as an innovator or a source of new ideas. This is supported by Lumpkin and Dess (2001), the research identifies entrepreneurs has the innovative skills to enhance new values to their own business.

In consequence, an innovative entrepreneur plays an important role to upgrade the economic of an individual as well as contributing to the country. Besides, Gelaidan and Abdullateef (2017) entrepreneurs able to produce new ideas, able to transform the ideas into a profitable business, creative innovative processes and producing employment.

Besides, entrepreneurship is a dynamic process of vision, change and creation. it demands the use of energy and passion to create and implement new ideas as well as creative proposals (Kuratko, 2005). Moreover, Kuratko (2005) interprets an entrepreneur as one who manages, administers and bears the risks of a business.

According to Hardy Loh et al., (2015) entrepreneur is a person with a unique instinct to see changes as an opportunity for value creation. Furthermore, entrepreneurs are visionary, able to conceptualise and implement business plans and possess an inspirational mind-set.

On the whole, entrepreneurship is a knowledge and skill to set up a business. Entrepreneurs able to think and produce ideas innovatively in their own business to upgrade economy at the same time producing employment. It encompasses networking skills, idea creation, developing and implementing a business plan, running a business and evaluating the internal and external business environment.

2.2 What Is Entrepreneurship Education?

Entrepreneurship education is not something new to the education system. The idea of infusing entrepreneurship into education has spurred much in the last few decades. As a result, entrepreneurship education enhanced economic growth, job creation, individual growth, improved school involvement and improved equality. Although, there is also important question whether entrepreneurship can be encouraged through education (Barba Sanchez & Atienza Sahuquillo, 2018).

According to Ivanov et al., (2012) education is the only platform to play essential role in the evolution of an entrepreneurial society. Entrepreneurial education is a source to provide

concepts, skills, knowledge and built their self-esteem to grab job opportunities (Zahari et al., 2018). Nevertheless, many universities and educational institutions providing entrepreneurship training programs to develop entrepreneurship skills among the students (Rosa Maria et al., 2019).

The Ministry of Education Malaysia has included entrepreneurship education in the New Primary School Curriculum and the Integrated Secondary School Curriculum since 1990s (Ministry of Education Malaysia, 2011). Entrepreneurship skills integrated in all the subjects as an element of across the curriculum. While, entrepreneurship skills taught through life skills subjects in lower secondary schools. At the same time, entrepreneurship skills are implemented in elective subjects such as trade and basics of entrepreneurship subjects in upper secondary school.

However, the content of this curriculum emphasis on the knowledge for students about the processes for managing a business directly. Aspects of student development to become human beings who have entrepreneurial characteristics are only touched on indirectly. As a result of such methods, the resulting students were found to still not cultivate the characteristics of entrepreneurship in daily life (Curriculum Development Division, MOE, 2011). Thus, Ministry of Education Malaysia fostering an entrepreneurial culture across the curriculum starting from year one is important to create a curriculum that is relevant to current needs and future challenges in this 21st century.

In addition, teaching entrepreneurship education able to form a visionary generation that has a strong foundation in the aspects of knowledge, thinking skills, communication, creativity, innovative thinking, positive enthusiasm and good moral and ethical values in the context of entrepreneurship. Moreover, entrepreneurship education is a formal teaching that insist knowledge, skills and educate potential entrepreneurs. It's a pedagogical intervention that lets students to create knowledge, competencies and experiences to make it possible for students to initiate and participate in entrepreneurial activities.

2.3 Students with Learning Disabilities

Learning disabilities are individual diagnosed with difficulties in reading, writing, speaking, listening, spelling, reasoning or doing math. Students with learning disabilities have problems in receiving information through their senses. Thus, they face difficulties in processing the information accurately. According to Law on Individual with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA), (2004) learning problems occur in one or more problems occur in the basic psychological processes in writing or spoken language.

The definition of learning disabilities in line with IDEA proposed by Sana Ali & Rafi (2016). Learning disability is a retardation, disorder or delayed development in any one or more of the processes of speech, language, reading, spelling, writing, or arithmetic. These problems are due to disorder or deficiency in any one or more of the basic psychological processes involved in understanding or in use of spoken or written language.

According to Learning Disabilities Association of Canada (2017), learning disabilities refer to a number of disorders which may affect the organization, acquisition, retention, understanding or use of verbal or nonverbal information. These disorders affect learning in individuals with disabilities otherwise display at least average abilities essential for thinking and

reasoning. Besides, learning disabilities may cause impairments in one or more processes related to perceiving, thinking, remembering or learning. These include, but are not limited to: language processing; phonological processing; visual spatial processing; processing speed; memory and attention; and executive functions.

Department of development of people with disabilities, department of social welfare (2011) defines learning disabilities as brain intelligence that is inconsistent with its biological age. Those who fall into this category are students with late global development, down syndrome, and intellectual disabilities. This category also includes conditions that affect an individual's learning ability such as autism, ADHD, specific learning difficulties such as dyslexia, dyscalculia, and dysgraphia and mental retardation.

In short, students with learning disabilities can be categorized either by the type of information processing or by the specific difficulties caused by a processing deficit. Learning disabilities can be categorized within four broad categories such as spoken language, written language, arithmetic and reasoning. Students with learning difficulties can successful in their life with a proper guidance, recognition and intervention.

2.4 Entrepreneurship Skills

The purpose of Entrepreneurship education is to evolve entrepreneurial competencies through educational activities indirectly. Entrepreneurial competencies were interpreted as knowledge, skills and attitudes (Lackeus, 2015). There are three main themes in entrepreneurial competencies that effect the ability to be a successful entrepreneur. Therefore, entrepreneurship skills under the umbrella of entrepreneurial competencies.

According to Farrington et al., (2012) entrepreneurial competencies categorized into cognitive competencies and non-cognitive competencies. Cognitive competencies are very easy to teach and evaluate, whereas non-cognitive competencies require learning by doing and more difficult to evaluate (Moberg, 2014a). However, current educational policies emphasizing large scale assessment and international standardize test has led to give important to cognitive competencies than non-cognitive competencies. The researchers identified the negative impacts occurs due to neglected non-cognitive competencies among entrepreneurs or students (Farrington et al., 2012). Table 1 shows the entrepreneurial competencies and its sub themes accordingly with the interpretation.

Table 1: Framework outlining some key entrepreneurial competencies and their relation to cognitive and non-cognitive competencies.

	Main themes	Sub themes	Interpretation
competencies	Knowledge	Mental models	Knowledge on how to resolve without resources
		Declarative Knowledge	Knowledge on basic entrepreneurship, value creation, idea generation, marketing risk
		Self-insight	Knowledge on personal on how to be an entrepreneur
		Marketing skills	Marketing products, persuasion, dealing with customers, communicating for a vision
		Resource skills	Create business plan, financial plan,

	Skills		obtaining financing
		Opportunity skills	Recognizing and looking for business opportunity, Product/service/concept development skills
		Interpersonal skills	Leadership, give motivation to others, managing people, socializing
		Learning skills	Be an active learner, adopt new situations
		Strategic skills	Set a goal and focus on goals, defining a vision,
	Attitudes	Entrepreneurial passion	"I want", Need for achievement
		Self-efficacy	"I can", Belief in one's ability to perform given tasks
		Entrepreneurial identity	"I am/I value", Deep belief, Role identity, Values
		Proactiveness	"I do" Action oriented, proactive
		Uncertainty/ambiguity tolerance	"I dare". comfortable with uncertainty, adaptable
		Innovativeness	"I create". Innovativeness, creative
Perseverance	"I overcome". Ability to overcome		

Source: Adapted from (Lackeus, 2014)

Based on the table 1, there are six sub themes highlighted as entrepreneurship skills. There are marketing skills, resource skills, opportunity skills, interpersonal skills, learning skills and strategic skills. Though, the Ministry of Education emphasizes entrepreneurship skills in the Primary School Standard Curriculum through teaching and learning activities so that it becomes a culture in their daily lives (Curriculum Development Division MOE, 2011). There are five main objectives of the entrepreneurship skills highlighted by Curriculum Development Division as follows:

1. Practice an entrepreneurial attitude
2. Practice a way of thinking towards entrepreneurship in necessary situations
3. Practice simple basic sales management knowledge and skills in relevant activities of daily living
4. Produce knowledge-based products as well as technological and vocational skills
5. Practice good moral and ethical values in the context of entrepreneurship

Besides that, table 2 summarizes the main objectives and focus of entrepreneurship skills in the Primary School Standard Curriculum through teaching and learning activities.

Table 2: The main objectives and focus of entrepreneurial elements highlighted by Ministry of Education Malaysia.

Main Objectives	Focus	Interpretation
1. Practice an entrepreneurial attitude	Responsible for decisions	The willingness to take responsibility for the results is closely related to the strength of the student's internal self-control.
	Aware to the opportunities	Aware to their own abilities and take the opportunities available in the surrounding.

	Dare to take estimated risks	Students need to learn to manage risk and ensure that the risks taken are reasonable and commensurate with the rewards received.
	Creativity and innovation	Students who are provided with a creative mind will be able to solve problems logically as well as be able to generate ideas that can be implemented in the form of innovation.
	Flexibility	Students who practice an attitude of flexibility will have the ability to adapt to changes in the environment into creativity and innovative.
	Desire for immediate feedback	Students who have a strong desire to use knowledge to improve their performance. This attitude is closely related to the desire to learn from past mistakes.
	Future oriented	Students who are given exposure to future business patterns will have a desire to get involved in the field.
	Willingness to learn from mistakes	Accepting failure as an impetus to achieve success. Failure is a lesson so that the same mistakes are not repeated.
	Capable of leading	Students has the experience to lead, has knowledge of the technology and the environment.
	Achievement oriented	Students know the objectives and goals to be achieved in a matter. The objectives are an impetus to move students towards achievement.
	Resilient	Students dare to face various challenges and obstacles to succeed in a project. Students need to have high mental, physical and emotional strength while continuing to deal with all problems with perseverance.
	Tolerant of high uncertainty	Students continue to perform assigned tasks despite facing various possible situations as a result of not getting accurate information or unexpected changes. They need to have the patience to tolerate uncertain situations.
	High perseverance	Students need to be able to face various challenges to ensure success in their efforts.
	Can build social networks	Students can use social networks to forge collaborative relationships to obtain information or share resources.
1. Practice a way of thinking towards entrepreneurship in necessary situations	<p>Students need to be critical, creative and innovative.</p> <p>This will help them identify opportunities in the environment, so that they can continue to succeed or at least survive by their efforts.</p>	<p>The way of thinking towards entrepreneurship in the required situation involves nine main steps, namely:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The practice of observing the environment intentionally and purposefully 2. Analyze observations critically and creatively 3. Generate ideas from observations

		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Choose the best idea from many ideas 5. Improve selected ideas in the form of innovations 6. Evaluate ideas critically in context 7. Implement ideas in the form of abstract or concrete technological products 8. Adapting new ideas to the needs of society and the environment 9. Continuing to improve the quality of ideas
<p>2. Practice simple basic sales management knowledge and skills in relevant activities of daily living</p>	<p>Students can master the basic knowledge and skills of simple sales management if they constantly exposed to the matter in teaching and learning activities.</p> <p>Students who have an attitude and way of thinking towards entrepreneurship, students can practice basic business management knowledge and skills in a simple transaction in relevant daily life situations.</p>	<p>Basic knowledge and skills of simple sales management involving the following processes:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Plan a project carefully 2. Implement the project according to the steps provided 3. Monitor the project 4. Evaluate project implementation 5. The application of basic knowledge and management skills elements of buying and selling easily involves: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Managing money either in daily expenses or savings (ii) Manage easy daily buying and selling transactions (iii) Good consumerism practices
<p>3. Produce knowledge -based products as well as technological and vocational skills</p>	<p>Students who have learned a technique in their learning can create and produce competitive products based on technological and vocational knowledge according to their creativity.</p>	<p>Technological and vocational knowledge and skills based can be used in:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Producing knowledge-based as well as technological and vocational products 2. Produce the same product using different technologies 3. Produce products using a variety of sources or recycled sources
<p>4. Practice good moral and ethical values in the context of entrepreneurship</p>	<p>Practice good moral and ethical values in the context of entrepreneurship.</p> <p>The practice of good moral and ethical values in the context of entrepreneurship encourages students to behave responsibly to society.</p>	<p>There are five principles of good moral and ethical value practice in the context of entrepreneurship:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The principle of social responsibility - business must not cause harm to humans and the environment 2. Principle of fairness: practicing fair business 3. Human rights principles: the practice of respecting human rights 4. Principle of autonomy: businesses cannot deny the right to choose individuals

		5. Principle of Transparency: Business that is not misleading
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Source: Handbook of Entrepreneurship Education, Ministry of Education Malaysia (2011)

At the same time, Curriculum Development Division of Malaysia implemented entrepreneurship education for students with learning disabilities as an element across the curriculum. So that, some key points highlighted in the curriculum to achieve the aims of entrepreneurship education among students with learning disabilities in order to produce young entrepreneurs. There are similarities between aims of entrepreneurship education for primary school and the aims of entrepreneurship education for the students with learning disabilities.

“The application of entrepreneurial elements aims to shape the characteristics and practices of entrepreneurship to become a culture among students. Entrepreneurial characteristics can be applied through teaching and learning activities that can cultivate attitudes such as diligence, honesty, trust and responsibility as well as develop creative and innovative minds to drive ideas to market”.

Source: Curriculum Development Division, Ministry of Education Malaysia (2011)

In short, we can conclude that Curriculum Development Division, Ministry of Education Malaysia (2011) planned and designed the curriculum for students with learning disabilities to cultivate their entrepreneurship skills through education system. The curriculum revealed the aim of entrepreneurship skills for the students with special needs to develop their creative ideas in the job market.

2.5 Methodology

In this study, library review method used to collect data and results.

2.6 Result and Discussion

2.6.1 Importance of Entrepreneurship Skills for Students with Learning Disabilities

The entrepreneurship education has become an important agenda in planning educational policies in many countries in this 21st century. Policy-makers had developed initiatives to enable and encourage students with learning disabilities to involve in entrepreneurial activities (Wittenburg et al., 2013). Numerous studies show entrepreneurship education is significant in cultivating the spirit of entrepreneurship among students (Hardy Loh et al., 2015). The most common reason for promoting entrepreneurship skills among students with learning disabilities is because entrepreneurship is seen as an engine for economic growth and job creation. Thus, the students with learning disabilities should acquire the entrepreneurship skills to be successful in their daily life.

However, competition and employment opportunities for students with learning disabilities are a matter of debate in an effort to provide careers for this group of people. According to Noraini et al., (2015), issues or problems in obtaining employment for students with learning disabilities should be given serious attention due to the unsecured employment opportunities for

them. This is because students with learning disabilities face issues in getting a job, skills, level of ability and physical ability as well as society's perception of this students with special needs (Mat Daros et al., 2012).

Meanwhile, Noraini et al., (2015) stated that the lack of skills in line with the wishes of employers is also a barrier factor for students with special needs to get a job. This opinion is further evidenced by the opinion of Beisland et al., (2016) who stated that the abilities and capabilities of students with learning disabilities are still taken into account by employers. This causes the students with learning disabilities to be unemployed because no jobs are offered. The matter of concern is a total of 1,934 students with special needs who completed their secondary school education in 2012 but did not obtain employment opportunities (Malaysian Education Blueprint (MEB), (2013-2025).

Therefore, the question arises what are the weaknesses in managing career and vocational education for students with special needs in secondary schools due to students do not get employment opportunities. Based on the study of Noraini et al., (2015) there is no evidence to suggest that there is a continuum of education with employment opportunities after graduation for students with learning disabilities. It is proven that there are weaknesses in terms of curriculum with learning disabilities, especially in secondary schools (Mat Daros et al., 2012). Thus, the secondary school curriculum does not focus on vocational skills (Nasri et al., 2010). Accordingly, it can be concluded that students with special needs learning disabilities do not have employability skills (Samian et al., 2013). In addition, existing employability skills through vocational education do not necessarily meet the needs of employers (Yusuf et al., 2013). So that, entrepreneurship skills are crucial for the student with learning disabilities to overcome unemployment issues.

Employer's perception on student with learning disabilities as an unproductive person regardless of their education. According to Beisland et al., (2016) employers resist hiring person with disabilities because they underestimated their working capability. The employers expecting those who are well trained and skilled in entrepreneurial field to face the industrial challenges. Thus, skill-based training and coaching is needed to students with learning disabilities to full fill the employer's needs. Therefore, entrepreneurship skills are compulsory because it's a form of skill-oriented education where the students able to learn the entrepreneurship skills through training and vocational activities.

However, the government has taken the initiative to implement a career transition program for students with special needs in secondary schools through a guideline for the special needs students career transition program (Ministry of Education Malaysia Professional Circular No. 4, 2019). This career transition program is a form of effort to prepare students with special needs to get employment opportunities as well as master vocational skills to qualify them for work. Researchers argue that vocational skills, employability, entrepreneurship skills should be applied through a systematic module from the grassroots again, starting at the primary school level.

Furthermore, the economic sector now expects a knowledgeable and skilled workforce in the field of employment. Entrepreneurship skills can contribute to a field of employment that can support students with special educational needs by living independently without relying on the job market. This can reduce the number of students with needs from being unemployed because there are no job opportunities after school. A study conducted by Anizam et al., (2020)

has identified special education teachers integrate four elements that are sub-elements in entrepreneurial skills, namely product production skills, product marketing skills, business skills, and cost calculation skills through teaching and learning activities for the student with learning disabilities.

Although, students with learning disabilities labelled as impairment of ability to perform an activity like a normal person. Hence, they need one skill that can make them self-reliant without depending on others to survive. Thus, entrepreneurship skill is an essential for them to be independent. On the other hand, they also can contribute to the economic growth. Kuratko (2010) supported that vocational and technical oriented education for students with learning disabilities will strengthen their chances of independent living at the same time it will stimulate the entrepreneurial skills embedded by them.

Entrepreneurship skills which are taught during teaching and learning activities will enhance the students with learning disabilities to become self-employment. The self-employment activities conducted by them are collectively known as “necessity entrepreneurship” according to entrepreneurship literature (Williams & Round, 2009). Most of the people with learning disabilities choose for self-employment and start their own business with the skills they have (Rosa Maria et al., 2019). Studies strongly supported the benefits of self-employment among people with learning disabilities in different context. Europe and US data indicated self-employment rates higher than among people with disabilities. The Australian Bureau Statistics (2013) shows that people with learning disabilities are more likely to run their own business than the normal person with the ratio of 11.6 to 8.2 %. In addition, Hwang & Roulstone (2015) found 388,241 out of 915,217 persons with disabilities in South Korea identified as self-employed. Thus, entrepreneurship skills driven the students with learning disabilities to self-employed and contribute for independent living.

Nonetheless, studies indicated that students who are immersed in entrepreneurial activities shows higher level of innovativeness in their work and able to produce ideas in new way. Entrepreneurship skill is not just a skill acquisition whereas it is a skill to creating employment for their self and also for others (Omede et al., 2016). In short, it's a process of development based on creativity and innovative. Therefore, educational institutions such as schools and universities play an effective role on produce students with a greater entrepreneurship skill to acquire entrepreneurial attitudes (Mutluturk & Mardikyan, 2018; Dohse & Walter, 2012; Kusmintarti et al., 2018; Vanevenhoven & Liquori, 2013; Matlay, 2016; Henley et al., 2017).

According to National Policy of Nigeria on Education (2004) highlighted the importance of entrepreneurship skills for students with learning disabilities as follows:

1. Prepare the students with learning disabilities for useful living in the society
2. Provide them with saleable entrepreneurship skills relevant in the 21st century and beyond
3. Enable them to compete with their peers in developed world and technology development
4. Make them partners in small scale industries
5. Make them contribute to Nigerian information communication technological needs

6. Provide them with the knowledge, skills and motivation to encourage entrepreneurial success

Besides that, the researchers stated some importance and the prospect of entrepreneurship skills among students with learning disabilities. In view of, Inoegbu & Ezeanochie (2010) students who are acquire the entrepreneurship skills will be benefits on these aspects:

1. Opportunity for work-based experience
2. Opportunity to practice leadership skills
3. Opportunity to develop inter personal skills
4. Chance to planning, financial literacy, and money management skills
5. Improved academic performance
6. Develop problem solving and decision-making abilities
7. Job readiness and social psychological development

These opportunities and trainings will be able to produce productive students with entrepreneurship skills in line with the aim of National Education Philosophy of Malaysia.

Even so, Lackeus (2015) stated entrepreneurship skills is highly potential to produce interest, joy, engagement and creativity among students with learning disabilities. Besides, researchers found that studies show entrepreneurship skills increase the motivation, school engagement, lessen the student's boredom and dropout which is commonly faced by students with learning disabilities (Moberg, 2014a). Hence, Lackeus (2015) explained the relevancy and importance of entrepreneurship skills to an individual level, organizational level and societal level.

Table 3 shows an overview of relevancy and importance of entrepreneurship skills for student with learning disabilities.

	Individual level	Organizational level	Societal level
Job creation	We need the individuals who are capable to create job opportunities for self-employment and for others	Growing organizations create more job opportunities	Entrepreneurship and innovation skills are primary path for job creation
Economic success	Entrepreneurship skills will be able to lead economic success	Organizational renewal is fundamental to every firm's long- term success	Renewal processes are fundamental to the vitality of economics
Globalization, Innovation	People need entrepreneurship skills and capabilities to thrive in an ever-changing world	Entrepreneurial firms play an important role in changing market structures	Entrepreneurial market requires people with higher level general and entrepreneurship skills
Joy, Engagement, Creativity	Creation / value creation / creativity is a main source of joy and pride of people	Employee creativity and joy is essential for the performance of new and existing organizations	Economic wealth of nations correlates with happiness of its citizens
Societal Challenges	People can make a difference to society, and marginalized people can	Corporations can collaborate with small social entrepreneurship	Social entrepreneurship addresses problem in

	achieve economic success	initiatives to create social value	society that the market economy has failed to address
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Source: Adapted from (Lackeus, 2015)

Therefore, entrepreneurship skills are crucial for the students with learning disabilities to develop their skills in job creation, economic success, globalization, innovation, joy, engagement, creativity and societal challenges. So that, educational activities and programmes for student with learning disabilities should be tailored towards providing them with the needed entrepreneurship skills from primary school. This will ensure the students with learning disabilities to grab employment opportunities and contribute to the nation's economy.

3.0 Conclusion

In brief, sustaining entrepreneurship skills among students with learning disabilities is a productive venture in this 21st century. As a developing country, Malaysia needs to cultivate entrepreneurship skills among students with learning disabilities to be independent living by start their own business with necessary competencies. Thus, this will enhance the country to produce more job providers than job seekers. As we know before, aim of this study to contributes fundamental knowledge on entrepreneurship skills and the importance for students with learning disabilities. Future researchers, can be able to prepare themselves to explore more on the effectiveness of entrepreneurship skills among students with learning disabilities.

Acknowledgment

This paper is an output about the importance of entrepreneurship skills among students with learning disabilities from various researchers and context.

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